

USING TED TALKS TO ENHANCE ENGLISH LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

Having a good command of English has always been considered one of the main factors contributing to students' success, especially in the fourth industrial revolution. In order to motivate students to learn, lecturers should constantly look for suitable ways of teaching. Students' English levels are different from class to class; therefore, different teaching methods are desirable. Apart from the textbooks used for all classes, more interesting learning materials should be offered to students, especially those who are good at English. This article shows that TED talks can be used as an extensive listening material for pleasure in the classroom or at home. Students can improve their listening skills and gain valuable language input through a combination of extensive and intensive listening materials and procedures. In addition, some TED Talks suitable for students majoring in business are also recommended. With the positive result of the survey regarding the benefits our students get from TED Talks, it can be said that TED Talks can prove effective in the English learning process as well as students' improvement.

Key words: TED Talks, motivate, instructional materials, extensive listening, improvement

1 INTRODUCTION

English has a more and more important role to play in this time of global communication. Our students feel the need to improve their English; therefore, they often request recommendation for supplementary materials to practice English outside the classroom. For extensive listening materials, TED Talks can be considered. TED Talks have an educational focus and aim to inspire and educate viewers by opening their mind to new ideas. TED Talks not only help English language learners widen their knowledge, improve their vocabulary, comprehension and pronunciation, but also improve their reading, listening, reading, writing and presentation skills. In this article, I would like to share my own experience of using TED Talks as one of the extensive listening sources.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Jeremy Harmer (2013), when it comes to learning English, the more resources we have the better. Students can improve their listening skills through a combination of extensive and intensive listening materials.

2.1 Intensive listening

Most course books include CDs and DVDs which are portable and readily available; therefore, when teachers want their students to practice listening skills, they rely on recorded material to provide a significant source of language input. The recordings provide a wide range of situations and voices. Furthermore, the recordings offered in digital form enable teachers to play recorded tracks in class from computers.

2.2 Extensive listening

It is especially important to have both extensive and intensive listening material since it provides the perfect opportunity to hear different voices and can help students improve their pronunciation and speaking ability.

In extensive listening procedure, students are encouraged to choose for themselves what they listen to and to do so for pleasure and general language improvement so extensive listening can have a dramatic effect on a student's language learning. Extensive listening usually takes place outside the classroom and materials for extensive listening can be obtained from a number of sources. Students can download English language podcasts online, TED talks, etc.

In order to encourage extensive listening, we can have students perform a number of tasks. They can record their responses to what they listened, list the topics, summarise the contents or write comments.

2.3 TED Talks

TED Talks are a series of informative, educational, inspiring talks that present "Idea Worth Spreading" in 18 minutes (or less) about science, business, global issues, the arts and much more. TED Talks have appealed to a lot of the world's most important people like Bill Gates, Bill Clinton, Larry Page, etc. People around the world have easy access to TED Talks on the Internet and find them highly engaging and motivating. With transcriptions in English, TED Talks help the audience read what they have listened to.

3 METHODOLOGY

Participant profile

The research was conducted in the University of Economics, where students are supposed to be good at English.

The instrument

The data were gathered from a questionnaire for 56 students. All items in the questionnaire were written in Vietnamese in order to make sure that it would not take much time and to minimize any misunderstanding.

4 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

The data were gathered from the questionnaire for 56 students in three classes. It is not surprising that 100 % of the students think that learning English is very important. More than three quarters (78, 5%) of the students know about TED Talks through their teachers. Thus, it is recommended that teachers introduce TED Talks as a supplementary material source.

The result showed that TED Talks have positive effects on student learning. Most of the students (93%) rated TED talks as “very user-friendly” and “user-friendly” because they could use the website easily. 96% thought the topics on TED were very interesting and interesting; therefore, we can believe that TED Talks can keep our students interested. Half of the students would like to choose any topics while 43% like the topics related to business. However, lecturers should explain the reason why students should choose the topics related to business because these topics are more useful for them in the future. In response to the question on motivation, 82% of the students thought that they felt “very motivated” and “motivated” when watching a video on TED Talks. Almost all of the students (93%) thought that watching TED Talks help them improve their listening skill, while only 57% thought reading skill can be improved, followed by 48% and 29% for speaking and writing respectively. Surprisingly, more than 82% of the students thought that their presentation skill was also better by watching TED talks. In response to the question on discussion after watching, most of the students (93%) thought it was useful; thus, follow-up activities should be considered carefully and about 10 questions for each TED talk are moderate. More than half of the students thought TED Talks should be watched in class or at home. Although 60% of students have some difficulty understanding and 67% need subtitles in English while watching, most of the students (96%) provided a “yes” answer to the question “Will you recommend TED Talks to other friends?” This means our students think TED talks are really one of the most motivating learning tools.

Learning English is a process of great difficulty in which students may sometimes get bored and demotivated; therefore, any tool that can help to motivate the students in their learning should be taken seriously, and TED Talks seem to be the tool we have been looking for.

TED Talks can help students improve their pronunciation, vocabulary, the four skills and presentation skills. In terms of pronunciation, transcripts can help students recognize how to pronounce a word, use connected speech, weak sounds and improve their pronunciation. For vocabulary, learners make themselves familiar with new words and try to guess the meanings of these words from the context. They can note down new words and then look up the meaning in dictionaries. Regarding the listening skill, students are asked to look at the title and choose a talk they are interested in. If they think it is useful, they prepare to make a brief presentation and give questions to their classmates. This requires students to watch and listen actively. In addition to improving listening, TED Talks help students practice reading. Nearly 68% of our students need transcripts in English; therefore, while watching the videos, our students practice reading at the same time. To practice speaking, students are asked to make a brief presentation in class to recommend the talk they watch at home. Discussing in pairs or in groups also helps to improve this skill. As for writing, after each TED talk there is a comment section where students can

discuss or share their thoughts about the video. They can enter these debates or practice writing an essay. Last but not least, by watching TED Talks students can learn how to prepare for a presentation, for example, how to start or end, how to use illustrations on the screen and how to control their speech. Furthermore, students can learn how to use their body language and how to be more expressive.

5 RECOMMENDATIONS

From the results of the questionnaire, it is obvious that TED Talks can be used as one of the extensive listening material sources. There are some recommendations for using TED Talks in class and at home as well as for orientation towards topics related to economics and business.

5.1 TED Talks can be used in class

An introduction to TED Talks should be given to students in the beginning because it plays a significant role in leaving a good impression on students so that they can decide whether they are interested in watching subsequent TED Talks or not. In order to make the TED Talks more effective, pre-watching, while-watching and post-watching tasks should be conducted in the classroom.

Take the “10 ways to have a better conversation” by Celeste Headlee as an example of the first TED talk used in my classes. The talk was introduced as the following three steps.

Pre-watching tasks

Ask questions about the title.

Ex. ‘What do you think the speaker is going to say?’

Ask for students’ experience or background knowledge about the topic.

Ex. ‘What do you usually do to have a good conversation?’

Offer some key vocabulary used in the talk.

While-watching tasks

Have students take notes of the main ideas of the talk.

Have students take notes of what are the 10 ways to have a better conversation.

Students can note down any words and phrases they do not understand and then try to guess their meanings in the context, discuss with their classmates or ask for help from the teacher.

Post-watching tasks

Encourage students to use the language from the talk to discuss the topic in pairs or in groups.

Ask students to think of questions to ask the speakers based on what they have watched.

Have a debate between ‘for’ students and ‘against’ students.

Ask students to write a review.

Ask students to give their opinions of the TED talks.

Ask students to give their impressions of the TED talks.

Encourage students to present their own talk on the same topic.

5.2 How TED Talks can be used at home

Due to time constraints on learning English at UEH, not all of the TED Talks suitable for economic students can be exploited in class; therefore, most of the TED Talks can be used at home. If the first TED talk can leave such a good impression on students, they may watch them by themselves. Lecturers can suggest the titles that are related to students' major or require them to choose the TED Talks they are interested in from thousands of videos by themselves. In order to motivate students, teachers can encourage them by giving one plus mark to those submitting essays or comments on what they can learn from the TED Talks. Although students are asked to choose the topics on TED Talks website, a list of TED talks should be introduced in order to provide orientation toward economics and business (see Appendix).

6 CONCLUSION

It is essential that teachers use a variety of teaching methods as well as material sources to best benefit their students. Among those, TED Talks can be considered one of the effective online learning tools. The research results demonstrated tremendous benefits that TED Talks could bring to business students. Thanks to TED Talks, UEH's students can not only improve their language skills but also learn something related to business. Moreover, they are motivated and inspired to study English.

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APPENDIX

List of Ted talks recommended for students majoring in business

- 8 secrets of success

https://www.ted.com/talks/richard_st_john_s_8_secrets_of_success?language=en

- The single biggest reason why start-ups succeed

https://www.ted.com/talks/bill_gross_the_single_biggest_reason_why_startups_succeed

- 10 ways to have a better conversations <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=R1vskiVDwI4>

- Five ways to listen better

https://www.ted.com/talks/julian_treasure_5_ways_to_listen_better

- How great leaders inspire action

https://www.google.com/search?q=How+great+leaders+inspire+action&ie=utf-8&oe=utf-8&client=firefox-b-ab&gfe_rd=cr&ei=rbWaV6-FDoPM8gf5nJnAAw

- Three lessons on success from Arab businesswoman

https://www.ted.com/talks/leila_hoteit_3_lessons_on_success_from_an_arab_businesswoman?language=en

- What it takes to be a great leader today

https://www.ted.com/talks/roselinde_torres_what_it_takes_to_be_a_great_leader?language=en

- 3 ways to lose (usefully) control of your brand

https://www.ted.com/talks/tim_leberecht_3_ways_to_usefully_lose_control_of_your_reputation?language=en

- How to make work-life balance

https://www.ted.com/talks/nigel_marshall_how_to_make_work_life_balance_work?language=en